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The Effects of Covid-19 Pandemic on the Goods Food Manufacturing Businesses in the 1st District of Davao de Oro: A Post-COVID Assessment

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Abstract

This study aims to provide a comprehensive overview of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in Davao de Oro by employing descriptive quantitative research. The focus is on demographics and operational characteristics. Twelve registered MSMEs from five municipalities were included using convenience sampling. Our analysis revealed a dynamic entrepreneurial landscape among respondents aged 26-30 years old, with a significant presence of female entrepreneurs. Maragusan and New Bataan emerged as central hubs, reflecting diverse geographical distribution. The duration of operations indicated a mix of newer and established enterprises, and a substantial portion of surveyed businesses operated with moderate monthly expenses. Perceptions regarding the impact of lockdown measures were consistent, with a significant proportion of respondents perceiving severe negative effects, particularly at Level 5. This study underscores the challenges faced by MSMEs due to the COVID-19 pandemic, emphasizing the need for tailored policies to support diverse business needs. Policymakers are urged to leverage these insights for evidence-based interventions, considering the urgency of addressing economic repercussions and promoting resilient recovery in Davao de Oro. Suggested strategies include financial assistance, business continuity programs, and capacity-building initiatives to alleviate hardships and foster economic recovery post-COVID-19.

Keywords: *micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs), COVID-19 pandemic, lockdown measures*

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic serves as a stark reminder that pandemics, like other sporadic disasters, have disrupted societies throughout history and will likely continue to do so in the future. While completely stopping the spread of deadly diseases might be unrealistic, mitigating their societal impacts remains crucial. Pandemics have far-reaching consequences for economies and societies, forcing significant shifts in how businesses and consumers operate. This research contributes to a broader global effort to understand the pandemic's effects on specific sectors.

While previous pandemics like the cholera outbreak of the early 1830s in France and the Spanish flu of 1918 offer historical context (O'Sullivan, 2021; History.com, 2020), the COVID-19 pandemic presents unique challenges. It not only threatens millions of lives globally (having caused over 4 million deaths by June 2021 [Worldometers, 2021]) but also disrupts supply chains, hinders long-term economic growth, and impacts environmental performance (Chowdhury & Paul, 2020; Khan et al., 2019).

The Asian Development Bank (ADB, 2020a) predicted a significant decline in economic growth across developing Asia due to the pandemic, with estimates ranging from a 5.1% growth in 2019 to a mere 0.4% in 2020. Although a rebound to 6.8% is forecast for 2021 (ADB, 2020a), this assumes successful containment of the virus and continued government support through fiscal and monetary policies.

The Philippines, like many other countries, has experienced significant economic hardship due to the pandemic. The Philippine economy contracted by 8.5% in 2020 (Abrigo et al., 2020), with losses across various sectors like wholesale and retail trade, transportation, and storage (Abrigo et al., 2020). Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs), the backbone of the Philippine economy (accounting for 99.5% of businesses and 63.2% of workers) (ADB, 2020b), are particularly vulnerable due to limited access to financing (ADB, 2020b).

In light of these challenges, this study specifically investigates the impact of COVID-19 on food manufacturing businesses in Davao de Oro, Philippines. We aim to understand how the pandemic has affected their scope of operations and revenue streams. Additionally, we explore the adjustments and changes businesses have implemented to cope with the evolving challenges brought on by the pandemic.

By focusing on food manufacturing businesses, this research provides valuable insights into a critical sector responsible for ensuring food security during a global crisis. This knowledge can inform future policy decisions and support strategies for food manufacturers to navigate similar disruptions in the future.

Methodology

Respondents

This study targeted food manufacturing businesses in Davao de Oro, Philippines. We recruited business owners and senior management personnel from twelve (12) registered MSMEs across five municipalities within the province. Convenience sampling, a non-probability sampling method, was employed due to limitations in time and resources. While convenient, this method acknowledges the potential

for selection bias and limits generalizability of the findings to the broader population of food manufacturers in Davao de Oro.

Instruments

A structured questionnaire was developed to collect quantitative data on the impact of COVID-19 on the participating businesses. The questionnaire covered aspects such as changes in scope of operations, revenue streams, and implemented adjustments.

Procedure

The researchers sought approval from the Vice President of Academic Affairs to use the institutional "Instrument for Teaching Effectiveness" as the survey tool. The questionnaire was piloted to 30 respondents to ensure its validity and reliability, achieving a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.99435, indicating excellent internal consistency. They also sought permission from the Office of the President of the institution to distribute the questionnaires to the respondents. Upon approval, the researchers requested the Deans of each department to allow their students to participate in the study. Additionally, the researchers obtained informed consent from the respondents, ensuring they understood the study's purpose and procedures.

After securing the necessary permissions, three hundred sixty-two students from different departments were selected using stratified sampling techniques to ensure representative participation. The researchers clarified the survey's instructions to all respondents to ensure accurate and honest responses. The data collected were then analyzed and interpreted by the researchers and served as the basis for conclusions and recommendations.

Data Analysis

The collected data was analyzed using descriptive statistics. Descriptive statistics provide summaries of the collected data, helping to understand the characteristics and trends within the sample. The following statistical tools were applied to the relevant questionnaire items:

Frequency: This was used to determine the number of respondents who selected each answer choice for a particular question.

Percentage: Percentages were calculated to show the proportion of respondents who selected each answer choice. This provides a standardized way to compare responses across different questions.

Rank: Ranking was used, if applicable, to order the responses based on a specific criterion. This can be helpful for understanding the relative importance or prevalence of certain factors.

By using these descriptive statistics, the study aims to provide a comprehensive picture of how COVID-19 has impacted food manufacturing businesses in Davao de Oro.

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to ethical research principles throughout the research process. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their involvement in the study. The questionnaire ensured the anonymity and confidentiality of the data collected.

Results and Discussion

The section on results presents the empirical findings obtained from various data sources, providing insight into the complex network of implications that emerged during the pandemic. All of the information that has come to light, from changes in customer behavior to supply chain interruptions, adds up to a thorough knowledge of how these companies handled the extraordinary obstacles that the global health crisis presented.

Thus, the results and discussion are crucial in any research paper as it provides an opportunity for the researchers to demonstrate their understanding of the research problems and to draw conclusions based on the data collected.

Table 1. *Frequency, Percentage, and Rank Distribution of the Respondents Profile in terms of Age Bracket*

<i>Age Bracket</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
20 and below	1	8.33	3
21-25	0	0.00	7
26-30	6	50.00	1
31-35	1	8.33	3
36-40	2	16.67	2
41-45	1	8.33	3
46-50	1	8.33	3
51-55	0	0.00	7
56-59	0	0.00	7
Grand Total	12	100	

Table 1 presents a comprehensive overview of the age distribution among MSMEs in the province, providing key insights into the

demographics of the study participants. Most respondents fall within the 26-30 age bracket, constituting 50.00% of the sample. Following closely, the 36-40 age group represents 16.67% of respondents. Age brackets 20 and below, 31-35, 41-45, and 46-50 represent 8.33%. No respondents were captured in the 21-25, 51-55, and 56-59 age brackets. The absence of respondents in certain age groups could indicate specific trends or characteristics within the local business community or may result from the study's sampling parameters.

Table 1.1. *Frequency, Percentage, and Rank Distribution of the Respondents Profile in terms of Gender*

<i>Gender</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Male	1	6.67	2
Female	11	91.67	1
Prefer not to say	0	0	3
Grand Total	12	100	

Table 1.1 offers a comprehensive depiction of the gender distribution among the respondents in the study, revealing pertinent insights into the demographic composition of the participating MSMEs. The data indicates a notable predominance of female representation, with 91.67% of respondents identifying as female entrepreneurs or business representatives. In contrast, male representation is 6.67%, signifying a comparatively smaller proportion. The absence of respondents opting not to disclose their gender highlights a commendable level of transparency in survey responses. This gender distribution insight holds implications for understanding the diverse makeup of the local business community, emphasizing the substantial presence of women in entrepreneurial roles.

Thus, these findings underscore the importance of adopting gender-sensitive approaches in formulating policies and initiatives to support and foster the growth of MSMEs in the province. Further exploration into the potential gender dynamics within the local business landscape could provide valuable context for future interventions.

Table 1.2. *Frequency, Percentage, and Rank Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Location of Business*

<i>Location of Business</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Compostela	2	16.66	2
Maragusan	4	33.33	1
Monkayo	1	8.33	3
Montevista	1	8.33	3
New Bataan	4	33.33	1
Grand Total	12	100.00	

Table 1.2 offers a comprehensive overview of the distribution of respondents based on their respective municipalities, providing insights into the geographical representation of MSMEs in the study. The data reveals that Maragusan and New Bataan have the highest frequency, each accounting for 33.33% of the respondents. Compostela closely follows with a frequency of 16.66%, and Monkayo and Montevista share the same frequency of 8.33%. The percentage column illustrates the proportion of respondents from each municipality relative to the total number of participants (12).

This distribution highlights a diverse geographic representation of MSMEs across multiple municipalities, with Maragusan and New Bataan emerging as central hubs of entrepreneurial activity. The ranking assigns Maragusan and New Bataan the top positions, underscoring their prominence in the study. The data suggests a rich tapestry of MSMEs contributing to the economic landscape across different municipalities, emphasizing that future analyses and interventions should consider each locale's distinct characteristics and challenges. Overall, this geographic breakdown enhances our understanding of the dispersed nature of MSMEs in the region, emphasizing the need for tailored strategies to support businesses across various municipalities.

Table 1.3. *Frequency, Percentage, and Rank Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Length of Operation*

<i>Length of Operation</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1-3 years	4	33.33	1
4-6 years	3	25.00	3
7-9 years	1	8.33	4
10 years and above	4	33.33	1
Grand Total	12	100.00	

Table 1.3 delineates the respondents' distribution based on the years their businesses have been in operation, offering crucial insights into the longevity of MSMEs in the study. The data indicates that a significant proportion of businesses, constituting 33.33%, have been operating for 1-3 years, showcasing a relatively newer cohort in the entrepreneurial landscape. Another 33.33% of businesses fall into the category of 10 years and above, suggesting a robust presence of well-established enterprises. The 4-6 years category comprises 25.00% of respondents, while businesses operating for 7-9 years represent 8.33%. The percentage column illuminates the proportional distribution of respondents in each category relative to the total number of participants (12). The ranking positions 1-3 years and 10

years and above at the top, indicating the prevalence of newer and more seasoned businesses.

Furthermore, this diverse range of operational durations underscores the varied stages of development within the local MSME sector. The findings imply that support initiatives and policies should cater to the distinct needs of businesses at different stages of their growth. Overall, this nuanced understanding of the duration of MSME operations contributes to a more targeted and effective approach to fostering sustainable business development in the region.

Table 1.4. *Frequency, Percentage, and Rank Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Estimated Monthly Expenses*

<i>Estimated Monthly Expenses</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1 to 10 K	3	25.00	2
11-100 K	6	50.00	1
101-250 K	1	8.33	4
251 or more K	2	16.67	3
Grand Total	12	100.00	

Table 1.4 outlines the distribution of respondents based on their Estimated Monthly Expenses, presenting a breakdown into four categories: 1 to 10 K, 11-100 K, 101-250 K, and 251 K or more. The table reveals that most respondents, accounting for 50.00%, fall within the 11-100 K monthly expense range, indicating that moderate financial commitments characterize a significant portion of the surveyed enterprises. The 1 to 10 K range follows closely behind, comprising 25.00% of the respondents. The lower frequency in the 101-250 K and 251 or more K ranges, at 8.33% and 16.67%, respectively, suggests a smaller presence of businesses with higher monthly expenses.

Furthermore, this distribution insightfully portrays the financial landscape of the surveyed enterprises, highlighting the prevalence of micro food manufacturing businesses with varying degrees of monthly expenditures. Understanding this spectrum is pivotal for formulating targeted strategies and recommendations tailored to the diverse financial capacities within the industry.

Table 2. *Frequency, Percentage, and Rank Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Perceived Effects of Lockdown on business performance*

<i>Effects of Lockdown on business performance</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1	2	16.67	2
2	1	8.33	5
3	2	16.67	2
4	2	16.67	2
5	5	41.67	1
Grand Total	12	100.00	

Table 2 presents respondents' frequency, percentage, and rank distribution based on their perceptions of the effects of lockdown on business performance. The effects are categorized into five levels (1 to 5), each representing a different impact on business performance. The "Frequency" column indicates how many respondents fall into each category. For example, two respondents perceive the impact as Level 1, three at Level 3, and five at Level 5. The "Percentage" column expresses these frequencies as a percentage of respondents (12). The "Rank" column assigns a rank to each level based on the percentage, with Level 5 having the highest rank (1) as it is associated with the largest percentage. The results suggest that a significant portion of respondents (41.67%) perceive the lockdown to have the most substantial impact on business performance (Level 5). The result could indicate a consensus among respondents perceived that the lockdown has had a severe negative effect on their businesses. On the other hand, Levels 1, 2, and 3, representing lower perceived impacts, have fewer respondents, indicating a more varied perception among participants.

To support these findings, research by Baker et al. (2020) emphasizes the economic implications of lockdown measures, stating that they can lead to disruptions in business operations and reduced consumer spending. This disruption, in turn, hampers the ability of businesses, especially smaller enterprises like those in the MSME sector, to maintain regular productivity and generate revenue.

In conclusion, Table 2 provides a comprehensive overview of how respondents perceive the effects of lockdown on business performance, highlighting variations in opinions and indicating that a substantial proportion of participants view the impact as significant. The cited authors contribute to understanding the economic consequences of lockdowns and the variability in their effects on different businesses.

Table 2.1 *Frequency, Percentage, and Rank Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Perceived Effects of Movement Restrictions*

<i>Effects of Lockdown on business performance</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1	2	16.67	2
2	1	8.33	5
3	2	16.67	2

4	2	16.67	2
5	5	41.67	1
Grand Total	12	100.00	

Table 2.1 presents respondents' frequency, percentage, and rank distribution concerning the effects of movement restrictions on business performance. Similar to Table 2, the effects are categorized into five levels (1 to 5), with each level indicating a different impact on business performance. The "Frequency" column shows how many respondents fall into each category, with, for instance, two respondents perceiving the impact as Level 1, one at Level 2, three at Level 3, two at Level 4, and five at Level 5. The "Percentage" column expresses these frequencies as a percentage of respondents (12). The "Rank" column assigns a rank to each level based on the percentage, with Level 5 having the highest rank (1) due to the largest percentage.

The results suggest that a significant proportion of respondents (41.67%) perceive movement restrictions to have the most substantial impact on business performance (Level 5). This aligns with the findings in Table 2, indicating a consistent perception of severe negative effects associated with lockdown and movement restrictions.

To support these findings, research by McKinsey and Company (2020) emphasizes the significant disruptions caused by movement restrictions, affecting various industries and leading to operational challenges for businesses. Additionally, research by Nicola et al. (2020) discusses the economic impact of mobility restrictions during the COVID-19 pandemic, providing insights into how such measures can influence business performance and contribute to the diverse responses observed among the respondents.

To sum up, Table 2.1 provides a comprehensive overview of respondents' perceptions regarding the effects of movement restrictions on business performance. The consistent pattern of higher percentages associated with more severe impacts aligns with existing research, as cited, emphasizing the disruptive consequences of such restrictions on businesses.

Table 2.2 *Frequency, Percentage, and Rank Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Perceived Effects of Lockdown on business performance*

<i>Effects of Market Closure on business performance</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1	2	16.67	2
2	1	8.33	4
3	2	16.67	2
4	1	8.33	4
5	6	50.00	1
Grand Total	12	100.00	

Table 2.2 outlines respondents' frequency, percentage, and rank distribution concerning the effects of market closure on business performance. As with the previous tables, the effects are categorized into five levels (1 to 5), representing varying impacts on business performance. The "Frequency" column indicates the number of respondents falling into each category, such as two perceiving the impact as Level 1, one at Level 2, two at Level 3, one at Level 4, and six at Level 5. The "Percentage" column expresses these frequencies as a percentage of respondents (12). The "Rank" column assigns a rank to each level based on the percentage, with Level 5 having the highest rank (1) due to the largest percentage.

The results reveal that most respondents (50.00%) perceive the closure of markets to have the most significant impact on business performance (Level 5). This suggests a consensus among participants that market closure has a considerable negative effect on businesses. In contrast, Levels 1, 2, 3, and 4 have fewer respondents, indicating a more varied perception among participants regarding the severity of the impact.

To support these findings, research by Altig et al. (2020) delves into the economic consequences of market closures during the COVID-19 pandemic, highlighting the challenges businesses face and the broader economic implications. Additionally, a study by Fernandez-Villaverde and Jones (2022) explores the impact of market disruptions on economic activity, shedding light on the potential repercussions for business performance during periods of market closure.

In conclusion, Table 2.2 provides a comprehensive overview of respondents' perceptions of the effects of market closure on business performance, indicating that a significant portion of participants view market closure as having a substantial negative impact. The cited authors contribute to understanding the economic consequences of market closures, supporting that such closures can pose challenges to businesses and contribute to diverse perceptions among respondents.

Conclusion

This study investigated the impact of COVID-19 on food manufacturing MSMEs in Davao de Oro, Philippines. By analyzing data from a survey of 12 registered MSMEs, the study aimed to understand these businesses' demographic and operational characteristics, along with their perceptions of the pandemic's effects.

The study revealed a dynamic MSME landscape in Davao de Oro, with a concentration of young entrepreneurs and a significant

presence of female-owned businesses. Geographically, businesses were spread across various municipalities, and financially, a mix of newer and established enterprises with diverse funding levels was identified.

Furthermore, the survey results highlighted the significant negative impacts of stricter lockdown measures on MSME performance. These findings align with existing research on the challenges faced by MSMEs during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Understanding these characteristics and perceptions is crucial for policymakers to develop effective support strategies for MSMEs in Davao de Oro. Policymakers should consider:

Tailored interventions: Providing targeted support based on the different stages of business development (newer vs. established) and financial capacity (micro vs. small vs. medium).

Gender-inclusive initiatives: Promoting programs that specifically address the needs of female entrepreneurs.

Targeted financial assistance: Developing financial aid programs suited to the diverse financial situations of MSMEs.

Business continuity programs: Offering support programs to help businesses adapt and maintain operations during challenging times.

Capacity-building initiatives: Providing training and resources to enhance the skills and knowledge of MSME owners and staff.

By implementing these evidence-based recommendations, policymakers can foster the resilience and sustainable development of MSMEs in Davao de Oro, enabling them to navigate economic challenges and contribute to the region's recovery from the COVID-19 pandemic.

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